

The Skill Of Opening A Child's Spirit Through Artwork

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Abstract

Literary critics, educators, and psychologists around the world unanimously emphasize the ideological importance of children's literature in raising a thoughtful and open-minded generation. Familiarity with children's literature teaches children to think figuratively, refines their tastes, and instills positive emotions in their hearts. Our people, who understood this very well, have since ancient times taught children various poetic verses, verses and prayers from a young age. In modern Uzbek literature, a category of writers has emerged who create exclusively for children.

In our country, the education of our future leaders has become an increasingly important task. One of the main factors in improving the quality of education is the instillation of a love of books, science, and especially literary literature, and a desire to read in the minds of the younger generation. As our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "We must raise young people to be independent and logical thinkers, possessing noble virtues, based on modern knowledge and experience, national and universal values."

Keywords : Poetic works, children's psyche, Artistic images, children's poetry, children's literacy.

INTRODUCTION

Children are often called "read-averse" by publishers. Many publishers only promote books that are easy to read. They believe that children will only choose books that meet their needs and are understandable in a modern context. However, recent pedagogical research shows that to get children interested in reading, they need to go beyond easy-to-read, meaningless stories. Traditional poems, fantasy poems, and humorous poems confirm the importance of poetry in developing children's reading skills and broadening their worldview.

The term "children's poetry" is a difficult concept to define. According to the formal definition, it means poetry written for or aimed at children. However, this definition is inadequate, because it does not reflect the diversity of forms and languages that this concept encompasses². Each

student can define children's poetry based on their own childhood experiences or the poems they are currently reading to their children. These definitions may differ dramatically, but they can serve as a source of information for explaining the meaning that fits this understanding. Children's poetry includes such poems, whose language and form are works that are accessible to children or that children can understand and enjoy. However, this is not a complete definition, because the phrase "poems that children can understand and enjoy" is not clearly defined. This definition limits children's poetry only in its simplicity. When adults read a wide range of poetry, including works translated from other languages or that address complex issues, they are able to appreciate how broad the term "child" is and how children can often understand much of this poetry.

Children need not only simplified and easy-to-read stories, but also poems and works with a rich creative and deep content. Traditional poems develop the structure of language in children, allow them to feel the harmony and rhythm of their native language. Fantasy poems expand the scope of children's imagination, encourage them to discover new worlds. Humorous poems not only make children laugh, but they also help to increase their vocabulary and develop their logical thinking skills. It is not enough for children to rely solely on "easy" books to learn to read. Poetry serves as a language learning tool for children and allows them to learn new ideas. Poetry is an important literary form that develops children's literacy and allows them to broaden their worldview. For this reason, children's literature should be rich not only in simple stories, but also in meaningful and unique poetic forms. A child often experiences feelings that are complex and difficult to understand, and putting them into words is often even more difficult. Poetry offers children a safe and healthy way to express these feelings. In this process, the poet may be a child, or the author may create a poem that they have written for children to read. In both cases, poetry helps to understand different emotions and find ways out of difficult situations.

In the world of children's poetry, mood is often expressed through vivid imagery, figurative language, specific scenes, or specific emotional states. Sometimes it is clear what the author is trying to convey through the poem, but sometimes the child or reader interprets the poem based on their own feelings and understandings. This process allows the child to express his inner feelings, and he actively participates in the understanding of emotional intonation.

A child who feels that he has successfully understood poetry feels confident, which helps him learn new words and phrases to express his feelings. In this way, poetry not only contributes to the

emotional development of children, but also to their linguistic development.

Modern children's poetry plays an important role in depicting the child's psyche. Poetry is not only spiritual food for children, but also a means of understanding and developing their inner world. Modern children's poetry offers a form and content that is more suitable for the modern child's consciousness than in previous eras. This article analyzes the specifics of depicting the child's psyche in modern children's poetry and its influencing factors. Children's poetry allows not only to express emotions, but also to expand the worldview of young readers, to explain life realities in a way that is close to the heart. The reflection of the child's psyche in modern children's poetry is implemented in several directions. Firstly, poems, with their content, help children more easily understand the joys and complexities of life. Secondly, the events and images depicted in the poem are conveyed through a melody and expression that is suitable for the children's psyche.

One of the important methods of depicting the child's psyche in poetic works is imagery and emotional richness. For example, when depicting the soul of a child, mental states are revealed through natural landscapes, vivid images, and life events. In the poems written for children by Kavsar Turdiyeva, the changes in the child's soul are skillfully reflected through various states of nature and the lives of animals. This not only helps children identify their feelings, but also helps them express them correctly. Elements of humor and play also play a large role in modern poetry. Through this method, poets manage to attract the attention of children and increase their interest in poetic works. Humor provides a sense of humor for children and gives them positive emotions. In this way, children's poetry fulfills not only moral and educational tasks, but also contributes to their spiritual health. Another effective means of

depicting the child's psyche is to create a dialogue tone. Poets of the new era use the form of dialogue to find a common language with children, to gain access to their inner world. For example, the characters in the poem face similar situations in children's lives and show them how to find solutions. In this way, children learn through emotions and events that are close to them.

Another important aspect is the musicality and rhythm of the melody of the poems. The rhythmic structure of poems is of great importance in influencing the child's psyche. The appropriateness of rhythm and melody makes it easier to remember the poem and gives children an aesthetic taste. Rhythm is especially important for young children, as it increases their understanding of and interest in poetic works. Modern children's poetry not only achieves its creative goals by depicting the child's psyche, but also plays a significant role in the personal and social development of children. Poetic works enrich children's moral understanding, teach them important values, and form a positive outlook on life. Therefore, modern children's poetry continues to develop its own unique approaches to deeply studying the child's psyche and expressing it.

For example, Abdurakhmon Akbar uses a comparison with nature to describe the psyche of a child. In Abdurakhmon Akbar's poem "What is Strong?", the image of a child's psyche is revealed in a poetic manner through comparisons with surrounding events and natural forces. The poem reflects the natural curiosity of young children in understanding the environment, the thinking process that is shaped by their questions and the answers they find. The comparison of natural forces of winter, such as snow, wind, ice, and snow, in the opening part of the poem expresses the child's desire for discovery. The interest in determining which of these forces is the strongest reflects the child's quest to understand the world.

In the next section, the sun is depicted as the most powerful phenomenon through the image of "Momo the Sun." The image of the sun being stronger than everything, shining even when clouds block it, conveys to the child the interconnectedness of natural forces and the necessity of the sun for life. This process focuses the child's mind not only on the harsh winter scenery, but also on the existence of positive forces that overcome this cold. At the end of the poem, the child creates a logical basis to support his reasoning: if the sun were afraid of the cold, it would not rise in the sky. Through this line, the poet depicts the logical thinking of a child and expresses the courage and invincibility of the sun in a childishly simple and sincere way. At the same time, the predominance of optimism and hope in the child's psyche is clearly demonstrated. In general, poetry serves as an important tool for shaping children's understanding of life. Through images that evoke positive emotions in the child's psyche, the reader is encouraged to imagine the world in a more holistic and positive way. The idea that it is possible to overcome cold and difficulties through the image of the sun creates a strong motivation in the spiritual world of children.

Kavsar Turdiyeva's poem "Uncle Uyku" is remarkable for its subtle and fresh interpretation of the child's psyche. The poem is an example of a creative and psychological approach in Uzbek children's literature, depicting the inner world of the child's psyche, the world of imagination and the clarity of fantasies. The hero of the poem - the embodiment of "Uncle Uyku" - is depicted as an unnatural image, different from the real world. This image is shaped by the child's imagination, and it expresses the incomprehensible and interesting elements in the life of every little one. The invisibility and harmlessness of "Uncle Sleep" reflects the need for innocence and peace inherent in children. In particular, his shoes made of "pamy, cotton or fleece" and his silent walk illuminate the

idea that inanimate objects in the children's imagination also have their own "life". Through this image, K. Turdiyeva expresses children's attitude to sleep in an unconventional way. The fact that children are not "attempted" to fall asleep, but rather that they adapt to it as a natural process in their lives, emphasizes the freedom of the child's psyche. This approach is also pedagogically important, because the need not to force children, but to work in harmony with their inner world is expressed through the symbols in the poem.

The figurative means and playful expressions used in the poem serve to enhance the aesthetic sensitivity of the child's psyche. The child who reads this poem experiences "Uncle Sleep" not as some real hero, but as a friend of his imagination. Each line of the poem, approaching the child's inner world, speaks of his inner peace and tranquility. This not only shows a new interpretation of the child's psyche, but also that children's literature is being liberated from the didactic approach. That is, the child's psyche, which has undergone transformations, is manifested in the form of a lyrical hero who, in harmony with the times, has been liberated from constraints and does not wait for an impetus to fulfill his desires.

Dilshod Rajab's poem "Varraklar Kuvonchi" deeply depicts the experiences associated with the child's psyche. The work reveals the harmony of the child's psyche with nature, the boundless expression of joy and happiness with its own unique skill. The poem interprets the inner connection between man and nature through the eyes of a child, reflecting the innocent and imaginative colors of the creative world of childhood. The poem begins with a harsh and cold winter scene: "The sleigh has passed / The bitter frost of winter." This is an attempt to assess the severity of winter from a child's perspective. This situation reveals children's sensitivity to the seasons and their tendency to express their feelings through

the changes in nature. The joy of spring, which comes with the departure of winter, is reflected by the poet through lively and joyful images. The reflection of the joy of nature in the inner world of man is even more vividly manifested in the continuation of the poem. For example, in the line "Nature is happy in clothes / In a festive dress" the interpretation of spring as a season of renewal is observed. This image shows the ability of the children's worldview to see beauty even in ordinary events. The child imagines nature "dressing up", that is, with the child's imagination he feels the aesthetic beauty in the change of seasons. In the next part of the poem, attention is paid to the sky: "The sky is blooming / The lightning flashes." These verses depict the joy of a child through the spectacle of nature in motion. The "laughter" of the sky is expressed through lightning, and the child turns this natural phenomenon into a symbol of joy. Under the child's gaze, the elements of nature acquire human qualities and, like the child, "they burst into laughter." Such personification brings nature to life, enhancing the feeling of closeness to it. The last part of the poem expresses the boundless joy of the child's soul through the boiling movement of nature: "Unbearable joy / The boiling springs." The bubbling of springs and streams is a figurative expression of the vibrant emotions in the child's inner world, a picture that perfectly matches the mood of cheerful and free children, moving without restraint. Here, the harmony of nature with the child's imagination is masterfully implemented. In general, the poem "The Joy of the Peacocks" expresses the natural, innocent, and boundless state of a child's soul, overflowing with joy. The poet's depiction of natural phenomena in a way that fits the inner world of the child's soul serves to deeply express the child's feelings, reflecting his world through nature. The poem reveals the connection between man and nature, especially through the unique perspective of childhood. This allows us to

understand the colorful and vibrant world of childhood more deeply.

Dilshod Rajab's work portrays the child's spirit as open to innovation and prone to philosophical thinking. Therefore, the poet's poems often contain enigmatic and symbolic images. In particular, the poet's poem "The Tortoise's Message to the Nightingale" is notable for its richness in such metaphors:

*Take a branch and hang it,
I saw you dancing,
If you fall, you'll get into a swamp.
If you are honest, it is difficult.
Take a walk in the swamp.*

In Dilshod Rajab's poem "The Turtle's Message to the Nightingale", the child's psyche is interpreted with its own depth, and through the images of the turtle and the nightingale, human behavior, attitude to life's trials, and the manifestation of true strength are symbolically illuminated in the work. In understanding the child's psyche, the poet reflects the child's curiosity, critical thinking, and unique perspective on trials in the inner world. The poem expresses the child's unique logical and thoughtful view of life through the turtle's address to the nightingale. In the poem, the turtle addresses the nightingale and suggests testing its beauty and strength in flight under more difficult circumstances. The turtle's words: "I saw you dancing, but if you fell, you would be in a swamp," show that the child's psyche is inclined to test their inner strength, rather than accepting conventional beauty or success without limits. The child is not satisfied with mere external attractiveness; he wants to understand the deeper meaning and true strength in the face of difficulties. The turtle's critical attitude is a vivid expression of the spirit of childhood exploration. The desire for justice is a strong element in a child's worldview. While the turtle suggests testing the nightingale's abilities in harsh conditions, such as a swamp, the

poet demonstrates the ability of children to understand that any achievement can only be truly appreciated through difficulties and real trials. Here, the symbols of nature illuminate the child's connection with the environment and reveal his interest in understanding complex situations. The poem reflects the desire of children to test their abilities in real conditions through the turtle's words: "If you are honest, take a walk in the swamp." A child's ability to be strong or skillful in imagination is not only evident in favorable circumstances, but also in difficult situations. This not only demonstrates the child's critical thinking, but also his ability to develop himself and strive for success in any situation. The child's spirit is manifested in harmony with nature and adaptation to circumstances, and the call of the turtle expresses the inner interest of children in every situation of life. Dilshod Rajab has deeply interpreted the child's spirit in this poem. The dialogue between the turtle and the nightingale contains a symbolic meaning, illuminating the true essence of life's trials, strength, and true success. The innocence of a child's view of the world and the trustworthiness of meaningful events form the main idea of the poem. The poem explains to children in a simple but profound way that human life is full of trials and teaches them to appreciate the true value of any ability through its resistance to limitations. This work skillfully conveys to the reader the beauty and uniqueness of a child's world.

In general, modern Uzbek children's poetry uses a rich artistic, aesthetic and educational means to implement a new interpretation of the child's psyche. The methodological approach aimed at exploring and developing the inner world of children through Abdurakhmon Akbar's riddle poems, Kavsar Turdiyeva's word games, and Dilshod Rajab's emotional and philosophical poems was demonstrated with great skill. The children's lyrical heroes created by these poets play an

important role in shaping the worldview of modern children, instilling in them a spirit of curiosity and intellectual exploration. These poems not only expand the horizons of children's thinking, but also create the basis for their spiritual and emotional development.

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